
Co-Relates of Happiness among Working Married Couples

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to find co-relates of happiness among working married couples. The sample for the present investigation consisted of 375 working married couples from Tricity (Chandigarh, Panchkula and Mohali) and 375 from National Capital Region (Delhi, Noida and Gurugram). Standardized tools were used to measure various variables of the study namely- happiness, resilience, marital adjustment, and job satisfaction. The finding revealed that optimal happiness appears to be associated with being in the 30–40 years age group, having a graduate-level education, earning a moderate income, being in the early years of marriage and living in a medium-sized family. Husbands reported a slightly higher happiness than females whereas wives perceived significantly greater job satisfaction. Notably, marital adjustment was significantly higher in wives. On the other hand, husbands reported higher levels of resilience. This study has important implications for working married couples and counsellors.

Introduction

Happiness is a multifaceted psychological state often defined by a combination of life satisfaction, emotional well-being, and positive affect (Lyubomirsky, 2001). In the context of marriage, happiness reflects not only individual mental health but also the quality and dynamics of the marital relationship. With the rise of dual-income households, particularly in urban centers, the exploration of happiness among working married couples has gained renewed relevance (Kalmijn, 2019). The pressures of managing professional responsibilities alongside family and relationship demands create a complex environment that can both enhance and challenge marital happiness.

Gender roles, spousal support, and cultural expectations also influence the level of happiness experienced in dual-career marriages (Bianchi et al., 2012). In urban Indian settings such as Tricity (Chandigarh, Mohali, Panchkula) and the National Capital Region (NCR), these dynamics are further complicated by rapid socio-economic changes, shifting family structures, and increased professional competitiveness.

Despite a growing body of literature on marital satisfaction and happiness, there is limited research examining how these correlates function specifically among working married couples in urban Indian contexts. Given the cultural diversity, varying work environments, and evolving gender norms in regions like Tricity and NCR, it is crucial to understand the unique factors that contribute to or detract from happiness in these populations. This study aims to identify and analyze the key correlates of happiness among married couples where both partners are employed, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on marital well-being in contemporary society.

In early times, roles, duties and obligations of husbands and wives were rigidly prescribed. Therefore, there was hardly any chance to arise conflicts regarding roles and duties among each other. But the entry of women at workforce have changed traditional family dynamics and happiness. Now the time has changed from when the husband earned and the wife stayed at home to when husband earns and wife earns to. Today, mostly educated women of modern times seems to have a vision of gender equality. The percentage of females in regular employment in urban India has increased from 25.8% in 1983 to 33.3% in 2000 and now it is expected to reach 361 per 1000 females in the year 2026 (McNay, & Cassen, 2004). Striking a balancing between work and family responsibilities can be challenging for both couples. This issue becomes even more significant in a country like India where most of the household roles are gendered. A significant change is witnessed in the labour markets of India as the entry of multinational companies (MNCs) in the rapidly growing. Where the majority of couples are working 40-50 hours per

week and 53% of them are struggling to strike a balance between work and family. Multinational companies (MNCs) do play an important role in the economies of countries where their head offices are operating. MNCs engage in foreign investment and manages production or deliver services in multiple nations. As two sides of same coin, the operation of multinational companies has both advantages as well as disadvantages for country like India. Multinational corporations (MNCs) have a various impact on the significant affairs related to the happiness and lives of working married couples.

Balancing individual life with their career can lead to conflicts and dilemmas. Couples may need to establish strategies that integrates both their work culture and their cultural background. Organizations can support couples by encouraging an inclusive work environment that appreciates cultural diversity, promotes work-life balance, and provides resources for couples to address the challenges arising from cultural and work-related differences.

1.1 Happiness

The field of positive psychology defines happiness as a state of well-being that includes living a healthy life. A person who experiences positive emotions like joy, interest, satisfaction, enthusiasm and contentment seeks to maintain a positive attitude and experience infrequent negative emotions such as sadness, anxiety, depression and anger. Happiness is positively correlated with life satisfaction and an appreciation of life.

Happiness is defined as a continuous feeling of enjoyment, self-satisfaction, generosity, and delight arising from interest with oneself life and the belief that one will have a peaceful future. Emotions such as joy, interest, pride, love, comfort, gratitude, inspiration and hope are positive emotions that enhances our happiness and motivate us. Happiness is experienced when an individual goals are achieved or when they have positive engagement with their surroundings. It is a dynamic and individualized emotional state influenced by various factors such as career well-being, subjective well-being, social well-being, spiritual well-being, and emotional well-being. In scientific literature, happiness is referred as “hedonia,” in an individual’s life it involves the presence of positive emotions and the absence of negative emotions. Diener (2000) contributed to the understanding of happiness by identifying three dimensions: positive affect (experiencing pleasant moods and joyful events), the absence of negative emotions (fear, anxiety, stress, and life satisfaction).

1.1.2 Co-relates of Happiness and Marriage among Working Married Couples

Marriage holds significant meaning beyond its legal status. It plays an important role in regulating the reproductive behaviour of a couple. In modern times, many marriages end in separation or divorce. However, marriage remains an important status for individuals, offering a sense of security and satisfaction. Al-Darmaki et al. (2014) defined marital happiness as the extent to which spouses in a marital dyad perceive their relationship to be personally fulfilling and contributing to positive and healthy family functioning. According to Fincham and Beach (2010), couples who are happily married experience less mental and physical stress. A successful marriage is one in which both partners respect each other cultural values and principles they share common interests and committed to stay together under any circumstances. Marital happiness is a judgment made by a spouse that reflects the sense of well-being or satisfaction they experience in the relationship. Marriage is one of the strongest predictors of happiness. Theorists have found that adults who are happily married experience the smallest decline in overall life happiness.

In the dynamic and interconnected network of multinational corporations (MNCs) the impact of work on couple's lives extends beyond the office. For dual-earner, couples working in MNCs can significantly affect both their work and personal lives influencing their happiness and overall well-being. Considering factors such as work-life balance, career opportunities, marital adjustment, personality, coping strategies for stress, and social support is essential for fostering healthy, fulfilling relationships in the context of multinational corporations. These factors play a critical role in shaping the happiness of couples amidst the opportunities and challenges posed by the MNC environment.

Factors Fostering Happiness among Working Married Couples

Figure: 1.1 Factors Fostering Married Couples' Happiness

1.2 Resilience

The word resilience originates from the Latin verb *resilire* means "to leap back" or "to spring back." The root of resilience, *salire* means "to leap" reflecting the ability to recover quickly from difficult situations and life's challenges.

According to the American Psychological Association, resilience involves adapting to change, accepting and dealing with adversity, trauma, anxiety, threats, depression, stress, such as family problems, relationship issues, mental health challenges or workplace and financial stress.

Ungar (2008) defined resilience as an individual's ability to maintain a positive outlook on life navigating psychological, social, cultural, and physical resources and believe that things will work out in the end. This belief helps the person grow stronger and find meaningful solutions.

1.2.1 Co-relates of Happiness and Resilience among Working Married Couples

Building resilience in the adversity of challenges among working married couples contributes to long-term happiness. Resilience plays an essential role in the lives of working married couples helping them to navigate life's challenges while maintaining a healthy relationship. A Resilient couple learn, grow, and develop emotional strength to overcome setbacks, adapt easily to changes, and manage stress effectively. This enables them to successfully navigate difficult times and balance work and personal life. Resilience equips an individual with the ability to manage stress provide mutual support and improve their emotional well-being. They become better equipped to handle demanding deadlines, long working hours and challenges in their work environments. A Resilient couple form strategies to reduce stress, such as setting boundaries, practicing self-care and seek social support. Resilience helps them strike a balance by prioritizing quality time, maintaining open communication about their needs and expectations and finding mutual ways to support each other's goals. By effectively managing demands they maintain a healthy work-life balance. They encourage motivate and listen to each other concerns. This support network provides professional guidance during career transitions and work-related difficulties contributing to their mental and emotional health. They embrace new opportunities navigate career shifts and foster a sense of teamwork for personal growth. Resilience enables them to learn from setbacks, bounce back from failures and continuously develop their skills, leading to both personal and professional growth.

1.3 Marital Adjustment

The term marital adjustment refers to the adjustments that individuals feel after marriage. Several challenges arise in married life such as adjusting to a spouse, sexual adjustment, financial management,

adjusting to in-laws, and psychological or personality adjustments. A satisfying couple is characterized by love, empathy, care, understanding, acceptance of reality and mutual communication. Married couples who are successful in their marriage provide strength to each other build confidence and support. Many studies on marriage and marital adjustment have shown that early marriage can often lead to marital instability.

1.3.1 Co-relates of Happiness and Marital Adjustment among Working Married Couples

Marital adjustment is a universal issue. However, happiness and marital adjustment are influenced by mutual respect and understanding between couples. Establishing a supportive home environment within the family is key to a happier life. Currently, partners working in multinational corporations (MNCs) face many challenges in balancing their personal and professional lives as they navigate the demands of their careers while maintaining their relationship. The aim of this study is to explore how marital adjustment and happiness are affected by the complexities that working married couples in MNCs experience. As a result, the following issues may arise:

1. Time Management

Couples working in MNCs often have long working hours, frequent job travel, a competitive work environment, and demanding job schedules which can negatively affect the quality time they spend together. These time constraints can lead to decreased communication, emotional disconnection, and a decline in marital adjustment.

2. Work-Related Stress

The competitive nature of MNCs can significantly increase work-related stress among working couples. Maintaining a demand of professional and personal life can strain their marriage resulting to increased conflict, job dissatisfaction, reduced social support, and a decrease in overall happiness.

3. Balancing Work and Family

MNC jobs may require frequent travel, relocation, and long working hours, which makes it difficult for couples to balance work and family life. This imbalance can affect their relationship, leading to issues in marital adjustment and happiness.

4. Financial Factors

However, working in an MNCs provides higher income and financial stability which can positively impact marital satisfaction. Financial pressures, such as debt or unequal income distribution, can create tension and negatively affect happiness within the marriage.

5. Work-Life Integration

Creating a harmonious integration of work and personal life is essential for marital adjustment. Marriage is a lifelong process and MNCs should promote work-life balance initiatives, flexible working arrangements and supportive policies to encourage couples managing their professional and personal lives more effectively.

1.4 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in an employee's overall well-being and productivity. It is the positive emotional response an employee experiences when they feel content with their work, job conditions, and the organization they work for. Job satisfaction impacts not only the employee's career but also their personal life, contributing to holistic development. Hoppock (1935) was the first to address job satisfaction as a concept, seeing it as a pleasurable or positive feeling that comes from an individual's experience of their job and work environment.

Vroom (1982) defined job satisfaction as an employee's emotional stability toward their current workplace, emphasizing the role of the employee in the organization.

1.4.1 Co-relates of Happiness and Job Satisfaction among Working Married Couples

Happiness and job satisfaction are closely related. When an individual finds their work productive and enjoys what they do, it positively influences their overall happiness. Job satisfaction is strongly influenced by the efficiency and productivity of the organization, while absenteeism, employee turnover, alcoholism, irresponsibility, and lack of commitment lead to job dissatisfaction and reduce happiness. The job profile in multinational corporations (MNCs) can have both positive and negative effects on married couples working there. MNCs offer opportunities for career growth, higher salaries, and benefits, all of which contribute to the financial stability of a working couple. Additionally, MNCs may provide flexible work arrangements, such as remote work options, that help couples balance their personal and professional lives. However, the demanding nature of MNC jobs, including long working hours and frequent travel requirements, can strain the work-life balance for married couples. This may lead to challenges in spending quality time together, managing household responsibilities, and nurturing their relationship. The pressure to meet work expectations and deadlines can increase stress levels and negatively impact the couple's overall well-being.

1.5 Need of the Study

A successful married life contributes to satisfaction in all areas. Every individual aspires to have a successful marital life. This study explores the role of working married couples in their relationship focusing on aspects such as resilience, marital adjustment and job satisfaction.

Marriage is a social institution plays a crucial role in individuals' lives, offering companionship, emotional support, and shared responsibilities. In recent decade, significant changes have resulted in increasing number of married couples where both partners pursue their professional careers. This rise in dual-income households has transformed marital dynamics, as couples try to balance their work and personal lives. In India, where the traditional roles of women as homemakers and caregivers have been dominant, the entry of women into the workforce has created challenges in balancing work and family life. Over the past decade, Indian families have undergone rapid changes due to industrialization and modernization. Educational opportunities are now considerably greater than they were a decade ago, individuals are under constant pressure to balance their work and personal lives. Today, couples from all social classes are joining the workforce. As a result, they often struggle to spend quality time with their families, and long working hours have a lasting impact on their marital life. Consequently, personal, social, and sexual issues in their lives have become more widespread.

1.6 Objectives of the Study

The present research was designed keeping in mind the following objectives:

1. To assess the level of happiness among working married couples.
2. To find out gender differences with respect to happiness among working married couples.

1.7 METHODOLOGY

The aim of the present study was to examine “Co-relates of happiness among working married couples”. A systematic procedure was designed for conducting the investigation, analysis and interpretation of data. Snowball sampling technique was used in the study. The tools used in the study have also been highlighted. Questionnaire method was used for the data collection. For the data analysis, IBM SPSS statistical version 20. software was used.

1.7.1 Type of the Study

Descriptive research design was conducted to evaluate co-relates of happiness among working married couples.

1.7.2 Locale of the Study

The locale of this study was Northern India, a region that has experienced rapid digital and economic growth over the last two decades, particularly in the Information Technology (IT) sector. This growth has been characterized by the proliferation of Multi-National Companies (MNCs) and a significant rise in urban migration by young professionals, including working married couples. The dual-income household trend has become increasingly common in the IT industry, contributing to financial stability but also intensifying challenges in maintaining work-life balance. The target population of this study are working married couples in the IT sector, was found to be most concentrated in two economic zones: **the National Capital Region (NCR)** and the **Tricity Region**.

Both NCR (Delhi, Gurugram, Noida) and Tricity (Chandigarh, Mohali, Panchkula) are prominent satellite city clusters, developed strategically to main urban centres and support regional economic growth. These cities reflect modern urban living intertwined with corporate ecosystems, and provide realistic microcosms to study work-life dynamics in MNCs.

Satellite cities are designed with planned infrastructure, residential corporate integration, and mobility networks that influence how married couples manage their work and personal lives making them especially relevant to this study.

Table -1 Recommended MNC Count for Survey on the basis of Sample Selection

Region	Big MNCs	Medium MNCs	Small MNCs	Total MNCs	Total Couples (Est.)
NCR	30	20	10	60	375
TRICITY	25	20	15	60	375

Assumption: 6-8 married couples per MNC

Plan to Meet the Target Sample Size of 750 Married Couples

Data were collected from working married couples, with two employees per couple participating in the study. On average, six couples (12 to 16 individuals) were surveyed from each selected MNC, depending

on the organization's size and the participants' willingness. This approach ensured equal representation across companies of varying sizes in each region, providing balanced weightage. The sample included a diverse range of sectors and organizational cultures, thereby enhancing the breadth and applicability of the findings. This sampling strategy allowed for a comparative analysis of patterns based on both company size and regional variations among working married couples.

1.7.3 Target Population

The target population for the current study comprised working married couples. This demographic was chosen due to its relevance to the study's objectives, which focus on relationship between couples in dual-income households. Working married couples are particularly suited for such research, as they navigate the complexities of professional obligations and personal relationships on a daily basis.

From this triangulation of government data sources, it was estimated that NCR (specifically Delhi, Gurugram, and Noida) and the Tricity area collectively have a significant population of working married couples.

1.7.4 Sampling Technique

Snow ball sampling technique was employed to ensure the participants met the study criteria namely, being legally married, both partners currently employed and residing in the selected urban areas. The sample was balanced by gender, with equal representation of married males and females.

1.7.5 Inclusion Criteria

The investigator selected working married couples (25-45 years) who were fulfilling the following criteria

- Working married couples aged 25-45 years from National Capital Region Tricity and
- Those who were married and living together for a minimum of one year.
- Couples should work in a multinational company.

1.7.6 Exclusion Criteria. The criteria mentioned below was followed:

- Couples residing outside National capital region and Tricity.

- Those who are unmarried/ divorced/ widowed.

1.7.7 Tools Used

The selection of the tools was done keeping in mind the objectives of the study and efforts were made to ensure that the tools have adequate psychometric properties. Tool used for measuring various variables of the study have been stated in the Table 3.

- **Table- 2 Tools Used for Measuring Different Variables of the Study**

VARIABLES	TOOLS USED
Dependent Variable	
Happiness	Oxford Happiness Inventory, Argyle (2001)
Resilience	The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale, Connor and Davidson (2014)
Marital Adjustment	Marital Adjustment Questionnaire, Kumar and Rohatgi (2018)
Job Satisfaction	Asha Job Satisfaction Scale, Hingar et al. (2009)

1.8Oxford’s Happiness Inventory (2001)

The Oxford Happiness Inventory was developed by Argyle (2001) (Appendix -III). This questionnaire was administered to assess the perception of happiness among working married couples. It consists of 29 item questionnaires measuring the main components of happiness i.e. achievement and satisfaction, enjoyment and health. Subjects were asked to respond to the items by marking anyone of the six response options viz, strongly disagree, moderately disagree, slightly disagree, slightly agree, moderately agree and strongly agree is 1,2,3,4,5,6 and for negative items which are 1,5,6,10,13,14,19,23,24,27,28,29 in these items reverse score is applicable. The test-retest reliability coefficient of the scale was 0.90. The range of scores for different categories of happiness is given below:

Table3 Categories of Analysis along with Range of Scores used for Happiness

Category	Range of scores
Low	52-93
Average	94-135
High	136and above

1.9 The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (2012)

The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) was developed by Kathryn M. Conner and Jonathan R.T. Davidson (2012) (Appendix-IV). The CD-RISC is based on Conner and Davidson's operational definition of resilience, which is the ability to thrive in the face of adversity. Since it was developed in 2003, the CD-RISC has been tested in several contexts with a variety of populations and has been modified into different versions. This scale was used to assess the resilience between couples. It measures resilience or how one can equipped to bounce back after stressful events, tragedy, or trauma. The CD-RISC consist of 25-items i.e. I can adapt when changes occur, I have one close and secure relationship etc. Each item is rated on a 5-point scale of responses ranging from (zero to four) as not true at all (0), rarely true (1), sometimes true (2), often true (3), and true nearly all the time (4) except for items 2,4 and 6 in which case reverse is applicable. The total possible scores range from 0–100, which reveals that the higher the scores higher the resilience. This scale has good baseline sample reliability, Cronbach's α 0.87. The range of scores for different categories is given below:

Table 4 Categories of Analysis along with Range of Scores used for Resilience

Category	Range of scores
Low	Below 42
Average	43-69
High	69 and above

1.10 Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (2018)

The Marital Adjustment Questionnaire was developed by Dr. Pramod Kumar and Dr. Kanchana Rohatgi (1976) and further revised in 2018 (Appendix-V). The present questionnaire consists of 25 statements. The scale was administered to assess the perception of marital adjustment among married couples. There are two categories of responses "Yes" or "No" for each item. A "Yes" for positive item response is assigned a score of 1, except for negative items i.e., 4,19 in which case reverse is applicable. Higher the total score, the higher would be a marital adjustment among couples and the scoring system for the revised form of the marital adjustment questionnaire is given below

Sr. No.	Types of items	Always	Sometimes	Never
1	Positive	2	1	0
2	Negative	0	1	2

Table 5 Categories of Analysis along with Range of Scores used for Marital Adjustment

Category	Range of scores
Low	17 and below
Above Average	37 – 41
Below Average	24 – 28
High	48 above

The Reliability of marital adjustment questionnaire was established by the Test-Retest Method. It was found to be .71 (N=60) with an index of reliability of 0.84. The retest was given with a time interval of 3 weeks. The r- values, 0.49 and 0.71 respectively, were found to be significant at the 0.01 level. Validity - The face validity of the questionnaire appeared to be fairly high. The questionnaire was also validated against Singh's Marital Adjustment Inventory (Singh, 1972). The coefficient correlation between the questionnaire and Singh's Marital Adjustment Inventory for a group of 20 wives was found to be 0.71 with a reliability index of 0.84.

1.11 Asha Job Satisfaction Scale (2009)

The Asha job satisfaction scale was developed by Dr. Asha Hingar (2009) (Appendix-VII). The main aim of the test was to measure job satisfaction, focusing on various facilities and opportunities provided by an organisation for the growth and development among married couples. The scale consists of a five-dimensional scale comprising 50 items. The five dimensions include (I) salary and facilities (II) supervision, (III) promotion, (IV) work and (V) human relations. The split-half reliability of the scale using the Spearman Brown formula is 0.79. The answers of the respondents are given in two categories viz., agree and disagree. They are assigned score (1) for agree and (0) for disagree. Further items (16-30) are scored in reversed order i.e (0) for agree and (1) for disagree. The total range score from 0-50. Each job dimension score ranges from 0-10. The range of scores for different categories of job satisfaction is given below:

Table 6 Categories of Analysis along with Range of Scores used for Job Satisfaction Scale

Job Satisfaction Level	Scores
High Job Satisfaction	35-50
Average Job Satisfaction	25-34
Low Job Satisfaction	0-24

1.12 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter sequentially presents the results **of the present study** along with their interpretation in light of standard criteria **established** by researchers. It is systematically **aligned** with the objectives and **hypotheses** stated earlier. To achieve the objectives of the study, data **were** collected from 750 married adults (375 couples) **from the Tricity region** and 750 married adults (375 couples) **from the National Capital Region**. After scrutiny and editing of the data, the necessary statistical calculations **were performed to test the hypotheses**. This chapter presents an analysis of the collected data under the following subheads:

- 1 Percentage distribution of samples with respect to their socio-personal characteristics
- 2 Percentage distribution of Tricity samples with respect to their socio-personal characteristics
- 3 Percentage distribution of National capital region samples with respect to their socio-personal characteristics
- 4 Comparison between the mean scores of various variables of working married couples
- 5 Comparison between the mean scores of various variables of working married couples in Tricity
- 6 Comparison between the mean scores of various variables of working married couples in National Capital Region

1.12.1. PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF SUBJECTS WITH RESPECT TO SOCIO-PERSONAL CHARACTERSTICS

Percentage distribution of the sample according to their socio-personal characteristics has been given in Table – 7

Table 7: Percentage Distribution of Happiness Scores among Working Married Couples Across Demographic Variables

Variables	Category	Husbands	Wives	Total
Age	Less than 30 years	25.3	25.2	25.3
	30-40 years	44.	47.5	45.7
	Above 40 years	30.7	27.3	29.0

Educational qualification	Diploma	22.7	19.6	21.1
	Graduate	69.6	74.1	71.9
	Post graduate	7.7	6.3	7.0
Household income	10-20 lakhs	83.6	83.2	83.4
	Above 20 lakhs	16.4	16.8	16.6
No. of years of marriage	Less than 8 years	57.2	47.6	52.4
	8-16 years	39.2	46.3	42.7
	Above 16 years	3.6	6.1	4.9
Size of the family	0-4 members	28.5	14.1	21.3
	5-8 members	70.1	80.4	75.3
	9 and above	1.3	5.5	3.4

Table 7 presents the distribution of happiness scores among working married couples across various demographic factors such as age, educational qualification, household income, years of marriage and family size. The age-wise analysis reveals that the highest percentage of happy individuals falls in the 30–40 years age group, accounting for 45.7% of the total respondents (44% husbands and 47.5% wives). This suggests that couples in this age bracket tend to experience greater marital satisfaction, possibly due to career stability and established family life. Those below 30 years contribute 25.3% to the overall happiness score, while those above 40 years form 29%, indicating that happiness levels tend to decline slightly with age.

In terms of educational qualification, the majority of both husbands and wives are graduates, with an overall percentage of 71.9% (69.6% husbands and 74.1% wives). This indicates a strong correlation between graduate-level education and marital happiness. Diploma holders represent 21.1% and postgraduates comprise only 7%, suggesting that graduate education may provide a balanced level of awareness, communication and compatibility conducive to marital satisfaction.

Regarding household income, the data shows that 83.4% of the respondents belong to the income bracket of ₹10–20 lakhs per annum, with almost equal distribution between husbands (83.6%) and wives (83.2%). Only 16.6% of the respondents fall under the higher income group of above ₹20 lakhs. This finding suggests that while financial security is essential, a very high income does not necessarily equate to higher happiness among working couples.

When considering the duration of marriage, happiness appears to be more prevalent in the earlier years. Couples married for less than 8 years account for the highest proportion (52.4% overall, 57.2% husbands and 47.6% wives), indicating that happiness tends to be stronger in the initial phase of marital life. Those married between 8–16 years make up 42.7% and only 4.9% of respondents have been married for more than 16 years, reflecting a potential decline in happiness as the length of marriage increases, possibly due to accumulated responsibilities and lifestyle changes over time.

Family size also plays a significant role in marital happiness. Couples from medium-sized families (5–8 members) make up the majority at 75.3% (70.1% husbands and 80.4% wives), indicating that a supportive family environment with shared responsibilities may contribute positively to happiness. Smaller families with 0–4 members account for only 21.3%, while large families with 9 or more members represent just 3.4% of the total, possibly due to increased household burdens and limited personal space in larger family structures.

Overall, the data suggests that happiness among working married couples is influenced by a combination of demographic factors. Optimal happiness appears to be associated with being in the 30–40 years age group, having a graduate-level education, earning a moderate income, being in the early years of marriage and living in a medium-sized family.

1.12.2 PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF TRICITY SAMPLES WITH RESPECT TO THEIR SOCIO-PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Percentage distribution of Tricity sample according to their socio-personal characteristics has been given in Table – 8

Percentage distribution of subjects according to their socio-personal characteristics

N —————> 750 ADULTS (TRICITY)

(375 HUSBANDS + 375 WIVES)

Table 8: Percentage Distribution of Happiness Scores among Working Married Couples Across Demographic Variables in Tricity

	Husbands (%)	Wives (%)	Total
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				(%)
Age	Less than 30 years	31.5	27.5	29.5
	30-40 years	46.7	48.0	47.3
	Above 40 years	21.9	24.5	23.2
Educational qualification	Diploma	41.1	24.5	32.8
	Graduate	50.9	67.2	59.1
	Post graduate	8.0	8.3	8.1
Household income	10-20 lakhs	84.0	82.1	83.1
	Above 20 lakhs	16.0	17.9	16.9
No. of years of marriage	Less than 8 years	58.9	47.7	53.3
	8-16 years	39.2	45.9	42.5
	Above 16 years	1.9	6.4	4.1
Size of the family	0-4 members	47.2	12.5	29.9
	5-8 members	52.5	79.7	66.1
	9 and above	.3	7.7	4.0
Total		100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 8 provides insights into the distribution of happiness scores among working married couples residing in Tricity, categorized according to age, education, household income, years of marriage and family size. Age-wise analysis reveals that the majority of happy couples fall within the 30–40 years bracket, accounting for 47.3% of the total respondents (46.7% of husbands and 48.0% of wives). This age group appears to experience the highest levels of happiness, likely due to a balance between personal life and professional growth. Respondents under 30 years make up 29.5% of the total, while those above 40 years account for 23.2%, indicating a moderate decline in happiness with increasing age.

With regard to educational qualifications, the data shows that a majority of the respondents are graduates (59.1%), with a notably higher percentage of wives (67.2%) compared to husbands (50.9%). Diploma holders constitute 32.8% of the total, with a significantly higher percentage among husbands (41.1%) than wives (24.5%). Postgraduates are the smallest group, forming just 8.1% of the total. This suggests that graduate-level education is most strongly associated with happiness among working couples in Tricity, possibly due to better job opportunities, social mobility and shared intellectual compatibility.

In terms of household income, a large majority of the respondents fall within the ₹10–20 lakh annual income bracket, making up 83.1% of the total (84.0% husbands and 82.1% wives), indicating that this

income level may provide financial stability conducive to marital satisfaction. A smaller portion (16.9%) of respondents earn above ₹20 lakhs, showing that happiness does not significantly increase with higher income levels.

The duration of marriage also reflects a trend in happiness distribution. Couples married for less than 8 years represent the highest percentage of happiness at 53.3% (58.9% for husbands and 47.7% for wives), implying that the early years of marriage are associated with greater satisfaction. Those married for 8–16 years account for 42.5% and those with over 16 years of marriage represent only 4.1% of the total, reflecting a pattern of diminishing happiness with longer marital duration, which may be attributed to evolving responsibilities or shifting relationship dynamics over time.

Family size emerges as another important factor. The highest proportion of happy couples (66.1%) belong to medium-sized families of 5–8 members, with a significantly higher percentage of wives (79.7%) than husbands (52.5%) in this category. Small families (0–4 members) account for 29.9% of the total, though the data reveals a gender disparity, 47.2% of husbands versus only 12.5% of wives suggesting that women may derive more happiness from a larger support system within the household. Very large families (9 or more members) comprise only 4.0%, indicating that extended family size might present additional challenges to marital happiness.

In conclusion, the data from Tricity reveals that happiness among working married couples is most prominent in the 30–40 years age group, among graduates, with moderate household income (₹10–20 lakhs), during the early years of marriage and within medium-sized families. These findings align with broader social patterns and underline the influence of demographic variables on marital satisfaction in urban, working populations.

1.12.3 PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION SAMPLES WITH RESPECT TO THEIR SOCIO-PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Percentage distribution of subjects according to their socio-personal characteristics

N —————▶ 750 ADULTS (NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION)

(375 HUSBANDS + 375 WIVES)

Table 9 : Percentage Distribution of Happiness Scores among Working Married Couples Across Demographic Variables in the National Capital Region

		Husbands%	Wives%	Total %
Age	Less than 30 years	19.2	22.9	21.1
	30-40 years	41.3	46.9	44.1
	Above 40 years	39.5	30.1	34.8
Educational qualification	Diploma	4.3	14.7	9.5
	Graduate	88.3	81.1	84.7
	Post graduate	7.5	4.3	5.9
Household income	10-20 lakhs	83.2	84.3	83.7
	Above 20 lakhs	16.8	15.7	16.3
No. of years of marriage	Less than 8 years	55.5	47.5	51.5
	8-16 years	39.2	46.7	42.9
	Above 16 years	5.3	5.9	5.6
Size of the family	0-4 members	9.9	15.7	12.8
	5-8 members	87.7	81.1	84.4
	9 and above	2.4	3.2	2.8
Total		100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 9 presents a detailed distribution of happiness levels among working married couples in the National Capital Region (NCR), taking into account demographic variables such as age, education, income, years of marriage and family size. The data reveals that the largest proportion of happiness is observed among couples in the 30–40 years age group, constituting 44.1% of the total respondents (41.3% of husbands and 46.9% of wives). This aligns with typical life stages of stability in career and family. Interestingly, the percentage of those above 40 years is higher in NCR (34.8%) compared to Tricity, suggesting that older couples in NCR may experience relatively sustained levels of happiness. Meanwhile, couples under the age of 30 contribute 21.1% to the happiness scores.

Educational qualification shows a strong concentration in the graduate category, with 84.7% of total respondents holding a graduate degree (88.3% of husbands and 81.1% of wives). This dominance implies that graduate-level education plays a key role in marital happiness in NCR. Postgraduates form a small group (5.9%), while diploma holders are even fewer, comprising only 9.5% overall. Notably, diploma-level education is significantly more common among wives (14.7%) than husbands (4.3%).

In terms of household income, the majority of the respondents (83.7%) fall within the ₹10–20 lakh bracket, with a relatively balanced distribution between husbands (83.2%) and wives (84.3%). A smaller percentage (16.3%) falls in the above ₹20 lakh category, suggesting that a middle-income range remains sufficient for achieving happiness, with limited additional benefit observed at higher income levels.

The number of years of marriage also offers interesting insights. Couples married for less than 8 years represent 51.5% of the total, with more husbands (55.5%) reporting happiness in this category than wives (47.5%). Those married between 8–16 years make up 42.9% of respondents, while only 5.6% of the couples have been married for over 16 years.

Family size data shows that a vast majority of couples (84.4%) belong to medium-sized families (5–8 members), with minimal variation between genders. This indicates a preference for and satisfaction within extended but manageable household structures. Only 12.8% of couples live in smaller families of 0–4 members and an even smaller proportion (2.8%) belong to large families of 9 or more members, suggesting that very large or very small family units may not be optimal for marital happiness in the NCR context.

In conclusion, the analysis of working married couples in NCR suggests that happiness is highest among those aged 30–40, with graduate-level education, middle income (₹10–20 lakhs), a marital duration of less than 8 years and living in medium-sized families. These findings reflect a stable, educated and moderately affluent working population for whom balanced family structures and early marital years are key to happiness.

1.12.4 COMPARISON BETWEEN THE MEAN SCORES OF VARIOUS VARIABLES OF WORKING MARRIED COUPLES

Table 10: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Results Comparing Husbands and Wives on Various Psychological and Demographic Variables

Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value
Happiness	Husbands	3.321	0.538	4.329	.0001**
	Wives	3.199	0.554		
Job Satisfaction	Husbands	29.264	5.580	9.426	.0001**

	Wives	32.032	5.792		
Marial Adjustment	Husbands	29.655	6.432	4.048	.0001**
	Wives	31.000	6.439		
Resilience	Husbands	75.017	14.195	3.961	.0001**
	Wives	72.089	14.431		

*Significant at 0.05 level $p < 0.05$, **Significant at 0.01 level $p < 0.01$

The second objective of the research was to find out gender differences related to happiness among working married couples. It was hypothesised that there will be no gender differences with respect to happiness among working married couples.

Table 10 provides a comparative analysis of working married husbands and wives across a wide range of variables, including happiness, job satisfaction, marital adjustment and resilience. The data is presented in terms of mean scores, standard deviation, t-values and significance levels (p-values). Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the majority of the variables, indicating meaningful gender-based variations in perceptions and experiences.

The data is presented in terms of mean scores, standard deviation, t-values and significance levels (p-values). Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the majority of the variables, indicating meaningful gender-based variations in perceptions and experiences.

In terms of **happiness**, husbands reported a slightly higher mean score ($M = 3.321$) compared to wives ($M = 3.199$), with the difference being statistically significant ($t = 4.329$, $p = .0001$). **Job satisfaction** was higher among wives ($M = 32.032$) than husbands ($M = 29.264$), a highly significant difference ($t = 9.426$, $p = .0001$), suggesting that women in this sample derive more satisfaction from their professional roles.

Notably, **marital adjustment** was significantly higher in wives ($M = 31.000$) than husbands ($M = 29.655$), indicating stronger adaptive and emotional alignment within the marriage among women.

In terms of resilience, husbands reported a slightly higher mean score ($M = 75.017$) compared to wives ($M = 72.089$), with the difference being statistically significant ($t = 3.961$, $p = .0001$).

Figure:1 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives

Figure:2 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives

Figure:3 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives

Figure:4 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives

The obtained results for more happiness among husbands than wives were in the line with findings of Glenn and Weaver (1988) who indicated that married men were happier than married women. The possible justification of the obtained results could be that marriage improves men's sense of well-being, but women's happiness tends to diminish because of household responsibilities. However, they find it difficult to balance between work and family and can not accommodate enough to maintain a balance with in-laws.

In a study by Hori and Kamo (2018) in western countries gender difference was the predictor of happiness among married couples suggested that marital status was a strong indicator of happiness especially for men but not for women. The possible justification of the obtained result could be that on average men were more satisfied in life as compared to women because marriage provides benefits for men in male-dominated societies. In contrast, full time employment responsibilities for women as important primary caregiver increases work-family conflict and cancel out its positive effect for women.

The findings of the present study were contrary to the result of the earlier research conducted by Patel and Dhar (2019) which concluded that husbands were happier than wives. Also, the findings of the present were contrary to the research findings by Sharma et. al (2019) which reported husbands were happier than wives in their marriage.

One possible explanation for greater satisfaction experienced by women in jobs than men could be drawn from research by Clark (1997). As men are the primary leaders of the family, they expect to excel more in life to fulfil the needs of the family members therefore, they expect to earn more. However, wives have lower job expectations and it could be as result of gender pay differential, discrimination at the work place and reduced promotion prospects. Therefore, occupying jobs that may be worse than men and lower expectations may translate into higher satisfaction for women.

Research by bender et.al (2005) and Clain et.al (2015), women who dominated at workplace reported having higher job satisfaction than men may be because married women have more flexibility in job choice and can decrease their working hours and focus on more a balanced life but, men can't do it. However, wives after marriage appear to value their personal relations more than their professional life.

Husbands were found more resilient than wives. The justification of the possible result could be after experiencing stressful situations, women are more likely than men to report signs of anxiety or symptoms of distress. However, husbands tend to be cool and calm in all aspects of life. At the same time, wives easily get anxious in stressful situations. This has led some to conclude that women may be less psychologically resilient than husbands (Stratta et al., 2013).

after marriage woman has to change even their name, dress and food habits to all habits of daily routine, she leaves her parents' house and stays at her husband's house. Hence, she has to face a lot of changes. She has to equip herself and adjust to all the things. So naturally, she has to face more adjustment problems than their counterpart husbands (Jaisri and Joseph, 2013).

1.12.4 COMPARISON BETWEEN THE MEAN SCORES OF VARIOUS VARIABLES OF WORKING MARRIED COUPLES IN TRICITY

Table 11: Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test Results comparing Husbands and Wives on various Psychological and Demographic Variables in Tricity

Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value
Happiness	Husbands	3.330	0.549	2.625	.009**
	Wives	3.225	0.550		
Job Satisfaction	Husbands	29.115	5.626	7.485	.0001**

	Wives	32.277	5.941		
Marial Adjustment	Husbands	30.019	6.285	2.531	.012*
	Wives	31.192	6.411		
Resilience	Husbands	74.965	14.617	2.299	.022*
	Wives	72.557	14.064		

*Significant at 0.05 level $p < 0.05$, **Significant at 0.01 level $p < 0.01$

This table illustrates a comparative analysis between husbands and wives in the Tricity area across multiple dimensions, including happiness, social support, job satisfaction, family dynamics and personality traits. The results, expressed through means, standard deviations, t-values and p-values, reveal several statistically significant differences between the genders.

Husbands reported a slightly higher mean score in happiness (M = 3.330) compared to wives (M = 3.225), with a significant difference ($t = 2.625, p = .009$), suggesting that men in the Tricity region perceive themselves as marginally happier. Similarly, **wives reported significantly greater job satisfaction (M = 32.277 vs. M = 29.115),** with the most substantial difference in this set of variables ($t = 7.485, p = .0001$). Significant differences were also observed in **marital adjustment**. Conversely, **husbands scored higher in resilience (M = 74.965),** suggesting a slightly stronger ability to cope with stress and maintain adaptability.

Figure:5 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives in Tricity

Figure : 6 Means of Job satisfaction and Wives on Job Satisfaction in Tricity

Figure:7 Mean score of Marital adjustment among Husband and Wives in Tricity

Figure:8 Mean score of Resilience among Husband and Wives in Tricity

1.12.6 COMPARISON BETWEEN THE MEAN SCORES OF VARIOUS VARIABLES OF WORKING MARRIED COUPLES IN NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION

Table 12: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Results Comparing Husbands and Wives on Various Psychological and Demographic Variables in the National Capital Region (NCR)

Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value
Happiness	Husbands	3.312	0.528	3.502	.0001**
	Wives	3.173	0.559		
Job Satisfaction	Husbands	29.413	5.537	5.817	.0001**
	Wives	31.787	5.636		
Marial Adjustment	Husbands	29.291	6.564	3.188	.001**
	Wives	30.808	6.469		
Resilience	Husbands	75.069	13.778	3.303	.001**
	Wives	71.621	14.792		

Table 12 presents a comprehensive comparison between husbands and wives in the National Capital Region on various psychological, interpersonal and personality-related parameters. The analysis is based on mean scores, standard deviations, t-values and p-values, reflecting statistically significant gender differences in several key domains.

In terms of **subjective well-being**, husbands in NCR reported significantly higher **happiness** ($M = 3.312$) than wives ($M = 3.173$), with the difference being highly significant ($t = 3.502$, $p = .0001$). **Job satisfaction was significantly higher among wives** ($M = 31.787$) than their male counterparts ($M = 29.413$), showing a robust difference ($t = 5.817$, $p = .0001$), similar to patterns observed in other regions. On the other hand, **husbands reported higher resilience** ($M = 75.069$), indicating their greater adaptability and psychological strength in the face of stress or life challenges. **wives showed better marital adjustment**, all with statistically significant differences.

Figure: 9 Mean score of Happiness among Husband and Wives in National Capital Region

Figure: 10 Mean score of Job Satisfaction among Husband and Wives in National Capital Region

Figure:11 Mean score of Marital Adjustment among Husband and Wives in National Capital Region

Figure: 12 Mean score of Resilience among Husband and Wives in National Capital Region

1.13 Suggestions

1. Work-Life Balance

The ability to manage job responsibilities without compromising personal or family time and imbalance in work life can often leads to stress, fatigue, and conflict, negatively affecting marital happiness.

2. Quality of Communication

It is important to includes active listening, open dialogue, and emotional expression. Couples who communicate effectively tend to resolve issues quickly and maintain closeness.

3. Emotional Support

Couple who provides care, validation, and understanding during times of stress or emotional need tends to have good relation. Emotional support strengthens trust and partnership, especially in demanding work-life situations.

4. Shared Responsibilities

It is important to have equitable distribution of household chores, childcare, and eldercare. It reduces feelings of being overburdened and promotes fairness and mutual respect.

5. Financial Stability & Agreement on Money Matters

Stable income, budgeting, and aligned financial priorities reduce arguments. Couples who agree on spending and saving goals report higher satisfaction.

6. Time Spent Together

Engaging in shared activities like meals, outings, or hobbies builds emotional intimacy. Even brief, meaningful interactions help maintain closeness in busy routines.

7. Job Satisfaction

A fulfilling job contributes to positive mood and reduced work-related stress at home. Dissatisfaction at work can spill over into personal relationships, reducing happiness.

8. Intimacy and Sexual Satisfaction

Includes emotional closeness, affection, and physical relationship. A healthy intimate life is strongly associated with marital happiness and trust.

9. Conflict Resolution Style

Refers to how couples handle disagreements constructive vs destructive styles. Positive strategies like compromise, problem-solving, and calm discussion improve relationship quality.

10. Personality Compatibility

Similar values, temperaments, and life goals help in better understanding and fewer conflicts. Even differences, when respected, can complement and enrich the relationship.

11. Social Support System

Help and encouragement from extended family, friends, or colleagues. A strong social network can buffer stress and provide perspective in challenging times.

12. Parenting Satisfaction

Satisfaction with roles and cooperation in raising children. Harmonious co-parenting enhances marital satisfaction and reduces parental stress.

13. Mental and Physical Health

Good physical and emotional health enables better coping, interaction, and intimacy. Chronic stress, anxiety, or illness can reduce energy and availability for the relationship.

1.14 Future Implications

- Workplace policies can be improved by promoting flexible hours and family-friendly environments.
- Counselling practices can be enhanced with targeted interventions focusing on communication, emotional support, and conflict resolution.
- Educational programs such as pre-marital and relationship workshops can be designed to teach practical life and relationship skills.
- Public health and welfare schemes can be tailored to support mental well-being, parenting, and work-life balance.
- Future research can explore cross-cultural, gender, and longitudinal aspects of marital happiness.
- These measures together can strengthen family units and contribute to a more emotionally resilient and productive society.

References

- Parks, A. C., Della Porta, M. D., Pierce, R. S., Zilca, R., & Lyubomirsky, S. (2012). Pursuing happiness in everyday life: the characteristics and behaviors of online happiness seekers. *Emotion, 12*(6), 1222.
- Kalmijn, M., de Leeuw, S. G., Hornstra, M., Ivanova, K., van Gaalen, R., & van Houdt, K. (2019). Family complexity into adulthood: The central role of mothers in shaping intergenerational ties. *American Sociological Review, 84*(5), 876-904.
- Bianchi, S. M., Sayer, L. C., Milkie, M. A., & Robinson, J. P. (2012). Housework: Who did, does or will do it, and how much does it matter?. *Social forces, 91*(1), 55-63.
- Lyubomirsky, S., King, L., & Diener, E. (2000). The benefits of frequent positive affect: Does happiness lead to success?. *Psychological bulletin, 131*(6), 803.

- Al-Darmaki, F. R., Ahammed, S., Hassane, S. H., Seif Abdullah, A., Yaaqeib, S. I., & Dodeen, H. (2014). Antecedents and consequences of marital satisfaction in an Emirati sample: A structural equation model analysis. *Marriage & Family Review, 53*(4), 365-387.
- Hoppock, R. (1935). Job satisfaction.
- Hills, P., & Argyle, M. (2002). The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire: a compact scale for the measurement of psychological well-being. *Personality and individual differences, 33*(7), 1073-1082.
- Ungar, M. (2008). Resilience across cultures. *British journal of social work, 38*(2), 218-235.
- Connor, K. M., & Davidson, J. R. (2003). Connor–Davidson resilience scale. *Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale*.
- Kumar, P., & Rohtagi, K. (2018). Certain personality correlates of marital adjustment. *Indian Journal of Social Work, 45*(3), 325-30.
- Hingar A, Mittal U, Parnami M. (2008.). Manual of Asha Job Satisfaction Scale, Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
- Jaisri, M., & Joseph, M. I. (2013). Marital adjustment and emotional maturity among dual-career couples. *Guru Journal of Behavioral and Social Sciences, 1*(2), 71-84.